

DYNAMIC RATIONAL EXPECTATIONS MODEL AND COVID-19 ON MONEY DEMAND IN CARISI COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of the dynamic rational expectations model and covid-19 on financial system stability in China, America, Russia, Italy, Spain, and Indonesia. This study uses the VAR analysis method with testing using Eviews 10. The results of the VAR analysis show that there is a change in the effect of each standard deviation of each variable from being favorable to negative and vice versa, from being harmful to being positive in the medium term and the long time. These results explain different responses from the money supply variable and the inflation variable, both positive and negative reactions. This condition shows that all the variables studied are correlated with each other in the medium and long term.

Keywords: Dynamic rational expectations model and Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of monetary policy in maintaining the stability of money circulation. The development of the money supply reflects the development of the economy. The growing and developing economy causes the money supply also to increase. If the economy is more advanced, the portion of the use of currency (paper money and coins) is decreasing, replaced by demand deposits. (Rahardja and Manurung, 2008:324) (Andre et al, 2021) (Altig et al, 2020)

Tambunan (2011: 257) states that too much money circulating in the community will impact causing a lot of demand. Conversely, too little money is held by the community, resulting in low order in the community resulting in quiet production activities, leading to an economic recession (Armantier et al., 2011). 2020) (Auclert et al, 2020) (Baker et al, 2020). So the stability of the money supply means financial stability for high and sustainable economic growth (Balleer et al. 1, 2020) (Bayer et al. 1, 2020) (Miescu et al. 1, 2021).

Several large countries have been in the spotlight of other countries due to rapidly developing economic developments (Coibion et al., 2020). And a concern because the economy is in an unstable condition. Financial problems such as low economic growth, investment, exchange rates, and high inflation rates will arise. Ten countries have the most increased money supply, according to tradingeconomics.com. Including (1) China, (2) America, (3) Russia, (4) Italy, (5) Spain, and (6) Indonesia.

Figure 1: Money Demand Carisi Countries Sebelum dan Setelah Covid-19

Based on the graph above, it is known that JUB fluctuations occurred in CARISI Countries from 2019-to 2020. Before the covid-19 outbreak, JUB levels were stable in almost all CARISI Countries. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, JUB levels tended to increase. America, 2020/05 JUB increased by US\$ 3,653,200 from the previous year of US\$ 3,558,300, and the highest JUB occurred in 2020/11, which was US\$ 6,086,100. Then in China, there was a decrease in JUB in 2019/07 of US\$2,017,961, then increased in 2020/07 by US\$2,998,861. While in Russia, the highest JUB occurred in 2020/07 at US\$ 3,829,763.

Figure 2: Inflation development before and after covid19

In China, the highest inflation occurred in 2019/09 at 3.45% and then decreased in 2020/03 by 2.32%. Then in America, the highest inflation occurred in 2020/03 at 2.31% and then reduced again in 2020/05 by 0.37%. While in Russia, the highest inflation occurred in 2019/05 at 5.17% and then, decreased again in 2020/01 by 2.31% and then increased again in 2020/11 by 4.91%.

Inflation is a measure of the economy in Indonesia; therefore, the government must be able to control inflation from the variables that influence it, such as interest rates, the money supply, and the exchange rate of the rupiah against the US dollar (Larsen et al. 1, 2021) (Meyer et al. 1, 2021)) (Carroll et al., 2020). The money and growth literature analyzes the impact of inflation on growth, focusing on the effect of inflation on the steady-state balance of per capita capital and output (e.g., Orphanides and Solow, 1990) (Cavallo, A., 2020) (Cavallo et al., 2017).

There are three possible outcomes regarding the impact of inflation on output and growth: i) none; ii) positive, and iii) negative. Sidrauski (1967) established the first result, showing that money is neutral and super-neutral 1 in an optimal control framework considering the utility function's accurate money balances (M/P). Tobin (1965), who thinks money as a substitute for capital, determines the positive impact of inflation on growth; the result is the Tobin effect. The adverse effects of inflation on growth, also known as the anti-Tobin effect, are attributed mainly to cash in advance models (e.g., Stockman, 1981), which consider money as a complement to capital 2. in an optimal control framework considering accurate money balances (M/P) in the utility function.

Figure 3: Investment development before and after covid19

Based on the table and graphic above. It is also known that the investment rate has different fluctuations in CARISI countries from 2019-to 2020. Before the Covid-19 pandemic, there was a relatively high increase in investment in Amerika in 2019/04, which was US\$ 11,693,800 from the previous year of US\$ 4,307,300. Meanwhile, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the investment pace showed no investment movement in almost all CARIS Countries.

Kewal (2012) examined the effect of inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and GDP on the JCI. The results found that only the exchange rate significantly affected the JCI, while the inflation rate, SBI, and GDP growth did not affect the JCI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dynamic Rational Expectation Analysis

Changes in the supply of gold and demand for the stock of gold coins will change the price of the balance of PG/P. It is easier to use rational expectations in the dynamic gold standard model if the gold standard model is in linear form. For example, inflation expectations $[E_t p_{t+1} - p_t]$, gold money stock $[\ln(G_{mt}) = m_t]$, general price level $[\ln(P_t) = p_t]$, and nonmonetary gold-stock $[\ln(G_n) = q_t]$. The demand model for the stock of gold and nonmonetary money is:

$$m_t - p_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + e_t$$

$$q_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \pi_t + \beta_2(E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + v_t$$

$$\alpha_0 > 0, \alpha_1, \beta_1, \beta_2 < 0$$

If ΔG is the change in the total stock of gold, then the difference is estimated at $\theta m_t + (1-\theta) q_t$, if θ is the fraction of the actual gold held in gold coins. Relative price [$P_G/P = p_t$] and gold depreciation are a certain fraction of the period's nonmonetary gold demand [$t - 1$], q_{t-1} . Therefore equation can be written in linear form as follows:
 $\theta \Delta m_t + (1-\theta)\Delta q_t = \rho_0 + \rho_1 p_t + \rho_2 q_{t-1}$

$$\Delta m_t + \omega_3 \Delta q_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 p_t + \omega_2 q_{t-1}$$

$$m_t + \omega_3 q_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 p_t + (\omega_2 + \omega_3) q_{t-1} + m_{t-1}$$

Parameter value ω is $\rho_1, \rho_2 < 0, \omega_3 = (1-\theta)/\theta$ and $\omega_i = \rho_i/\theta$. Equation is used to find dynamic solutions of p_t, m_t , and q_t . Equations show two grace time variables [m_{t-1} and q_{t-1}] plus two shocks [e_t and v_t]. The solutions to the three equations can be written in reduced-form equations, where all endogenous variables are functions of all exogenous variables:

$$p_t = \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} q_{t-1} + \phi_{12} m_{t-1} + \phi_{13} e_t + \phi_{14} v_t$$

$$m_t = \phi_{20} + \phi_{21} q_{t-1} + \phi_{22} m_{t-1} + \phi_{23} e_t + \phi_{24} v_t$$

$$q_t = \phi_{30} + \phi_{31} q_{t-1} + \phi_{32} m_{t-1} + \phi_{33} e_t + \phi_{34} v_t$$

Evaluate the coefficient value ϕ_{it} can be done by defining price expectations in the period [$t + 1$] as follows :

$$E_t p_{t+1} = \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} q_t + \phi_{12} m_t$$

$$= \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} [\phi_{30} + \phi_{31} q_{t-1} + \phi_{32} m_{t-1} + \phi_{33} e_t + \phi_{34} v_t]$$

$$+ \phi_{12} [\phi_{20} + \phi_{21} q_{t-1} + \phi_{22} m_{t-1} + \phi_{23} e_t + \phi_{24} v_t]$$

Substitution to replace $[E_t p_{t+1}]$ and the model used includes but is replaced by the gold accumulation relationship, i.e.:

$$m_t + \omega_3 q_t = k$$

This means that the total gold stock is constant at k . To analyze the behavior of the price level in terms of and the substitution of:

$$p_t + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 (E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + e_t$$

$$+ \omega_3 [\beta_0 + \beta_1 p_t + \beta_2 (E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + v_t] = k$$

The bootstrap-free solution is that the price level is determined by random shocks $[e_t]$ and $[v_t]$. The bootstrap-free solution is

$$p_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t$$

Value $E_t p_{t+1} = \phi_0$ Substitution gives the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\alpha_1)[\phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t] + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \phi_0 + e_t \\ + \omega_3[\beta_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2)(\phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t) + \beta_2 \phi_0 + v_t] = k \\ (1-\alpha_1)\phi_1 e_t + e_t + (1-\alpha_1)\phi_2 v_t + \alpha_0 + \phi_0 + \omega_3 \beta_0 + \omega_3 \beta_1 \phi_0 \\ + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)[\phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t] + \omega_3 v_t = k \end{aligned}$$

The equation is fulfilled with three parameters or coefficients, namely:

1. $\phi_0 + \alpha_0 + \omega_3 \beta_0 + \omega_3 \phi_0 \beta_1 = k$ or $\phi_0 = [k - \alpha_0 - \omega_3 \beta_0] / [1 + \omega_3 \beta_1]$,
2. $(1-\alpha_1)\phi_1 + 1 + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)\phi_1 = 0$ or $\phi_1 = -1 / [1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)]$, dan
3. $(1-\alpha_1)\phi_2 + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)\phi_2 + \omega_3 = 0$ or $\phi_2 = -\omega_3 / [1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)]$.

Known value $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2, \alpha_1 < 0$ so that the value $\phi_1, \phi_2 < 0$. Therefore a positive surprise in demand for gold money $[e_t \geq 0]$ and a positive surprise in the market for nonmonetary gold $[v_t > 0]$ will temporarily lower the general price level. Therefore, increasing the demand for nonmonetary gold and gold coins will reduce the general price. The variance of the general price level with the average general price level $[\phi_0]$:

$$Var(p_t) = \frac{\sigma_e^2 + \omega_3^2 \sigma_v^2}{[1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3(\beta_1 - \beta_2)]^2}$$

Equation $E(e_t, v_t) = 0$ as the effect of each parameter value resulting in variations in the general price level, to obtain dynamic demand for gold $[m_t]$ and non-monetary gold $[q_t]$, namely:

$$m_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \phi_0 - (1 + \alpha_1) p_t + e_t \quad m_t = -[\phi_1 + \alpha_1 \phi_1 - 1] e_t - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_1 \phi_2) v_t$$

(1.39A)

$$q_t = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) p_t + \beta_2 \phi_0 + v_t$$

$$q_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \phi_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) \phi_1 e_t + [(\beta_1 - \beta_2) \phi_2 + 1] v_t$$

So that a positive surprise in demand for gold $[e_t > 0]$ and request for nonmonetary gold $[v_t > 0]$ will temporarily increase the demand for gold and nonmonetary gold. On the other hand, a

negative shock to demand for gold [$\epsilon_t > 0$] and request for nonmonetary gold [$\epsilon_t < 0$] will temporarily reduce demand for gold and demand for nonmonetary gold.

III. METODE PENELITIAN

The data collection technique used in this study uses a documentation study, namely collecting and processing data from previous information related to the problem under study. -2020. The data analysis model uses VAR analysis.

VAR Analysis Model with the formula:

$$JUB = B_{10} + B_{11}INF_{t-p} + B_{12}INV_{t-p} + B_{13}PDB_{t-p} + B_{14}SB_{t-p} + B_{15}IHK_{t-p} + B_{16}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{17}KURS_{t-p}\beta + E_{11}$$

$$INF = B_{18} + B_{19}INV_{t-p} + B_{20}PDB_{t-p} + B_{21}SB_{t-p} + B_{22}IHK_{t-p} + B_{23}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{24}KURS_{t-p} + B_{25}JUB_{t-p}\beta + E_{12}$$

$$INV = B_{25} + B_{26}PDB_{t-p} + B_{27}SB_{t-p} + B_{28}IHK_{t-p} + B_{29}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{30}KURS_{t-p} + B_{31}JUB_{t-p} + B_{32}INF_{t-p}\beta + E_{13}$$

$$PDB = B_{32} + B_{33}SB_{t-p} + B_{34}IHK_{t-p} + B_{35}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{36}KURS_{t-p} + B_{37}JUB_{t-p} + B_{38}INF_{t-p}\beta + B_{39}INV_{t-p} + E_{14}$$

$$SB = B_{40} + B_{41}IHK_{t-p} + B_{42}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{43}KURS_{t-p} + B_{44}JUB_{t-p} + B_{45}INF_{t-p} + B_{46}INV_{t-p}\beta + B_{48}PDB_{t-p} + E_{15}$$

$$IHK = B_{49} + B_{50}CADEV_{t-p} + B_{51}KURS_{t-p} + B_{52}JUB_{t-p} + B_{53}INF_{t-p} + B_{54}INV_{t-p}\beta + B_{55}PDB_{t-p} + B_{56}SB_{t-p} + E_{16}$$

$$CADEV = B_{57} + B_{58}KURS_{t-p} + B_{59}JUB_{t-p} + B_{60}eINF_{t-p} + B_{61}INV_{t-p}\beta + B_{62}PDB_{t-p} + B_{63}SB_{t-p} + B_{64}IHK_{t-p} + E_{17}$$

$$KURS = B_{57} + B_{58}JUB_{t-p} + B_{59}INF_{t-p} + B_{60}eINV_{t-p} + B_{61}PDB_{t-p}\beta + B_{62}SB_{t-p} + B_{63}IHK_{t-p} + B_{64}CADEV_{t-p} + E_{18}$$

Description:

JUB	: Money demand (Billion US\$)
INV	: Investation (Billion US\$)
INF	: Inflation (%)
PDB	: GDP (Billion US\$)
SB	: Interest Rate (%)
IHK	: Commodity Price Index (Point)
Cadev	: Foreign exchange reserves (US\$)
KURS	: Exchange rate (Billion US\$)
et	: random disturbance
p	: lag

IV. DISCUSSION

Table 1. Result Dynamic Rational Expectations Model

Vector Auto regression Estimates								
	LOGJUB	INF	LOGINV	LOGPDB	SB	LOGIHK	LOGCADEV	LOGKURS
LOGJUB(-1)	0.879380 (0.16005) [5.49443]	-0.326225 (1.09765) [-0.29720]	0.554442 (0.21588) [2.56832]	0.037324 (0.12207) [0.30576]	-3.318581 (1.65306) [-2.00754]	0.002001 (0.03886) [0.05150]	-0.032684 (0.09155) [-0.35699]	0.032743 (0.02284) [1.43352]
INF(-1)	-0.002174 (0.02049) [-0.10607]	0.563920 (0.14054) [4.01246]	-0.060114 (0.02764) [-2.17481]	0.016321 (0.01563) [1.04421]	0.127792 (0.21166) [0.60377]	0.003947 (0.00498) [0.79322]	0.013857 (0.01172) [1.18211]	-0.001132 (0.00292) [-0.38692]
LOGINV(-1)	-0.070399 (0.12743) [-0.55246]	-2.105377 (0.87393) [-2.40909]	0.774521 (0.17188) [4.50623]	0.101133 (0.09719) [1.04058]	-1.609503 (1.31613) [-1.22290]	-0.021968 (0.03094) [-0.71001]	0.052399 (0.07289) [0.71883]	0.037474 (0.01819) [2.06064]
LOGPDB(-1)	0.161367 (0.16974) [0.95068]	1.054616 (1.16410) [0.90595]	-0.008503 (0.22895) [-0.03714]	0.593553 (0.12946) [4.58488]	3.345859 (1.75313) [1.90851]	-0.001663 (0.04121) [-0.04035]	-0.021433 (0.09710) [-0.22073]	-0.006704 (0.02422) [-0.27675]
SB(-1)	0.003231 (0.01585) [0.20384]	0.182762 (0.10870) [1.68129]	-0.012150 (0.02138) [-0.56832]	-0.007183 (0.01209) [-0.59419]	0.135633 (0.16371) [0.82851]	0.001784 (0.00385) [0.46368]	-0.001759 (0.00907) [-0.19404]	0.001988 (0.00226) [0.87876]
LOGIHK(-1)	-0.416127 (0.83039) [-0.50112]	-10.38970 (5.69495) [-1.82437]	-2.959979 (1.12004) [-2.64274]	-0.202172 (0.63333) [-0.31922]	17.99365 (8.57658) [2.09800]	0.564636 (0.20162) [2.80050]	-0.162143 (0.47501) [-0.34134]	-0.082989 (0.11851) [-0.70030]
LOGCADEV(-1)	0.094461 (0.36769) [0.25691]	4.521494 (2.52167) [1.79306]	1.347239 (0.49594) [2.71652]	-0.192892 (0.28043) [-0.68783]	-2.327586 (3.79763) [-0.61291]	0.032392 (0.08928) [0.36284]	0.722541 (0.21033) [3.43526]	0.018691 (0.05247) [0.35619]
LOGKURS(-1)	-0.253967 (1.20287) [-0.21113]	9.348227 (8.24951) [1.13319]	-4.130694 (1.62245) [-2.54595]	-1.313160 (0.91742) [-1.43135]	29.16117 (12.4237) [2.34721]	-0.009259 (0.29206) [-0.03170]	0.188622 (0.68809) [0.27413]	0.454624 (0.17166) [2.64835]
C	1.095449 (3.14364) [0.34847]	-5.992963 (21.5597) [-0.27797]	10.73253 (4.24020) [2.53114]	4.195006 (2.39764) [1.74964]	-86.49937 (32.4688) [-2.66407]	0.861125 (0.76328) [1.12819]	0.620077 (1.79828) [0.34482]	1.104633 (0.44863) [2.46222]

The effectiveness of monetary policy is significant because it is used to determine which variables are the most dominant in the economy to be used as a basis for formulating monetary policy strategies (Coibion et al. 1, 2022) (Fetzer et al. 1, 2021) (Guerrieri et al. 1, 2020). Also, to find out how firm and long the deadlines for each transmission line work (Candia et al. 1, 2020) (Bordalo et al. 1, 2020) (Candia et al. 1, 2020). It is essential to determine which economic and financial variables are the most vital leading indicators of the movement of the money supply and which variables are indicators for determining the operational targets of monetary policy (Warjiyo, 2004) (Gornemann et al. 1, 2021) (D'Acunto et al., 2021) (Carroll et al., 2020). The relationship between monetary control instruments and the ultimate goal of monetary policy is indirect and complex. It requires a relatively long time (Binder et al. 1, 2020) (Andre et al. 1 2021) (Christelis et al. 1, 2020). Therefore, experts and practitioners in monetary add indicators are called operational targets. Following are the leading in monetary transmission policy:

Table 2: Leading Indicators Result in Dynamic Rational Expectations Model

Variable	Leading Indicator		
	1	5	10
JUB	JUB	JUB PDB	JUB PDB
INF	INF JUB	INF SB	INF JUB
INV	INV INF	INV KURS	INV KURS
PDB	PDB INF	PDB INF	PDB INF
SB	SB INV	SB INV	SB INV
IHK	IHK JUB	IHK JUB	IHK JUB
CADEV	CADEV IHK	CADEV INF	CADEV INF
KURS	KURS INV	KURS INV	KURS INV

1 = short-term

5 = middle-term

10 = long-term

The Leading Indicators are as follows:

- 1) The leading indicator to control JUB is JUB, both in the short term, medium-term and long term.
- 2) The leading indicator to control INF is JUB in the short and long term, while the SB is in the medium term.
- 3) The leading indicator to control INF is the exchange rate in the medium and long term, while INF is in the short term
- 4) The leading indicator to control GDP is INF, both short, medium, and long term.
- 5) The leading indicator to control SB is INV, both in the short, medium, and long term.
- 6) The leading indicator to control the CPI is JUB, both short, medium, and long.
- 7) The leading indicator to control CADEV is the CPI in the short term while the INF in the medium and long term.
- 8) The leading indicator to control the EXCHANGE is INV, both in the short term, medium-term and long term

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Money demand before sebelum covid19	1170.3747	12	151.56879	43.75414
	Money demand before after covid19	1313.5248	12	188.32933	54.36600
Pair 2	Inflation before covid19	2.8008	12	.19313	.05575
	Inflation after covid19	1.9708	12	.59920	.17298

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Money demand before and after covid19	12	-.855	.000
Pair 2	Inflation before and after covid19	12	-.390	.210

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Money demand before sebelum covid19	-143.15017	327.48549	94.53692	-351.22452	64.92419	-1.514	11	.158
Pair 2	Money demand before after covid19	.83000	.69763	.20139	.38675	1.27325	4.121	11	.002

Sumber: output reviews 2022

The average rate of money demand before the COVID-19 pandemic was US\$ 1170.37, and after the emergence of this pandemic, the JUB rate increased by US\$ 1313.52. The value of sig (2-tailed) for the money demand variable is 1.58, which means $> = 0.05$. Thus, based on the criteria for accepting and rejecting the hypothesis above, from the results table, it can be seen that the t count at sig (2-tailed) = 1.58 > 0.05 , the value of sig is greater than the error level of 5% so that, H0 is accepted. Ha is rejected. . This shows no significant difference in money demand before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The average inflation rate before the COVID-19 pandemic was 2.80%, and after the emergence of this pandemic, the inflation rate decreased to 1.97%. The value of sig (2-tailed) for the inflation variable is 0.02, which means $< = 0.05$. Thus, based on the acceptance and rejection criteria for the hypothesis above, from the results table, it can be seen that the t count at sig (2-tailed) = 0.02 $< = 0.05$, the value of sig is smaller than the error level of 5% so, Ha is accepted and H0 is rejected. This shows a significant difference in inflation before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

V. Conclusion

Dynamic Rational Expectations Model and Covid-19 on Money Demand in Carisi Countries showed that these results explain different responses from the money supply and inflation variables, both positive and negative reactions. This condition indicates that all the variables studied are correlated with each other in the medium and long term. During the Covid-19 period, all the countries studied experienced an economic recession and decreased demand for money due to reduced investment, fell GDP, and increased interest rates, thereby raising prices. The money supply after Covid-19 has changed due to changes in people's inflation expectations in the Carisi country. At the same time, the economic recession occurs due to macroeconomic instability from the impact of the absence of the economic downturn.

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